

Effect of 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium-based ionic liquid on the resolution of three components in Herba Artemisiae Scopariae by RP-HPLC

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Abstract : The chromatographic behavior of three components of Herba Artemisiae Scopariae, chlorogenic acid, caffeic acid and rutin on C₁₈ column was examined using different concentrations of a 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium tetrafluoroborate ionic liquid as an additive in acetonitrile/water (20/80, v/v) mobile phase. The results showed that 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium tetrafluoroborate, optimal concentration 0.5 mM, was quite effective in retaining the three components. The mechanism of retention of three components on C₁₈ column in the presence of ionic liquid additive has been discussed.

Keywords : [Bmim][BF₄], chlorogenic acid, caffeic acid, rutin, additive.

Introduction

Recently, room temperature ionic liquids (RTILs) have attracted considerable attention as an environmentally benign solvent for organic chemical reactions, separations and electrochemical applications¹⁻³. The most commonly used RTILs are composed of an imidazole, pyrrole, or pyridine based cations and an inorganic anion⁴. RTILs have been used as novel materials in a variety of separation methods, such as stationary phases in gas chromatography⁵, buffer electrolytes in capillary electrophoresis⁶ and mobile phase additives in HPLC⁷. When used as an additive in the mobile phases in reserved phase liquid chromatography to improve the separation of basic compounds, both the anionic and cationic components of RTILs contribute to solute retention as well as the improvement in peak shape, an effect due to their simple "salting-out" and ion pairing effects⁸. The addition of RTILs can suppress the silanol interactions on a C₁₈ column by HPLC. Furthermore, the silanol suppressing potency of RTILs strongly surpasses that of the standard alkylamine additives⁹⁻¹².

Herba Artemisiae Scopariae is a widely used traditional Chinese medicine that is prepared from the dried sprout of Artemisia Scoparia Waldst. et Kit. It is often

used as an important ingredient in many traditional prescriptions¹³⁻¹⁵. In addition to cholagogic effect, it also has other pharmacological actions such as protecting the liver, lowering blood pressure, as well as anti-inflammatory and antibacterial activity^{16,17}. The major active compounds in the herb are chlorogenic acid, caffeic acid and rutin. In order to evaluate the quality of Herba Artemisiae Scopariae in the marketplace, it is essential to establish a rapid, simple and accurate approach for separating them and determining their concentration.

In this study, a 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium-based ionic liquid (IL), 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium tetrafluoroborate ([Bmim][BF₄]), was first proposed as mobile phase additive for the separation of chlorogenic acid, caffeic acid and rutin by liquid chromatography. Fig. 1 shows the structures of chlorogenic acid, caffeic acid and rutin. The effects of [Bmim][BF₄] and the concentration of [Bmim][BF₄] on the retention behaviors of the samples were investigated and the optimum separation conditions were obtained. This method is considered suitable for evaluating the quality of Herba Artemisiae Scopariae. It proved a promising development trend for chromatography.

Fig. 1. The structures of chlorogenic acid, caffeic acid and rutin in *Herba Artemisiae Scopariae*.

Experimental

Materials and reagents :

Authentic standards of chlorogenic acid, caffeic acid and rutin were purchased from National Institute for the Control of Pharmaceutical and Biological Products, Beijing, China. [Bmim][BF₄] was offered by Professor Yoon-Mo Koo, Bioengineering Inha University, Korea. All other reagents were of analytical grade and purchased from Duksan Pure Chemicals Co., Ltd., Ansansi, Korea. The water used was doubly-distilled.

Apparatus and chromatographic conditions :

The HPLC system was equipped with Waters 600S

solvent delivery system including 616 solvent delivery pump, 600S controller and the 2487 UV dual channel detector and an injector (0.02 mL sample loop) of Rheodyne (Waters, Milford, MA, USA). The data acquisition system was Millennium32 (Waters) installed in a Samsung PC.

Separation was accomplished on C₁₈ column (4.6 × 250 mm, 5 μm). The flow rate was set at 0.5 mL/min. The wavelength was fixed at 325 nm. The mobile phases were adjusted to pH 4 with hydrochloric acid or sodium hydroxide solution. The separation was done at ambient temperature.

Preparation of standard solutions :

Stock solutions of chlorogenic acid, caffeic acid and rutin were prepared by dissolving their known amounts in methanol. Working standard solutions were prepared by suitably diluting the stock solutions with methanol. All solutions were prepared in dark brown calibrated flasks and stored at 4 °C when not in use.

Results and discussion

Effect of [Bmim][BF₄] on retention behaviors of the samples :

Figs. 3 and 4 show chromatograms of chlorogenic acid, caffeic acid and rutin in ACN/water (20/80, v/v) mobile phase without and with 0.5 mM [Bmim][BF₄] at pH 4, respectively. Chlorogenic acid and caffeic acid were not separated in the ACN/water mobile phase, however, get separated completely when 0.5 mM [Bmim][BF₄] was added to the mobile phase. In addition, the retention time of chlorogenic acid was decreased but of caffeic acid and rutin increased. All the peaks were sharper when [Bmim][BF₄] was used in the mobile phase.

A previous study of the mechanism of the [Bmim][BF₄] additive¹⁸ reported that the imidazolium cation existed not only in the bulk solution but was also coated on the capillary wall when used in CE. Therefore, ionic liquid exists in both mobile phase and as coated on the column when used in HPLC. Imidazolium cations can interact with silanol groups (shown in Fig. 2) and compete for the silanol groups on the alkylsilica surface with the polar

Fig. 2. Proposed scheme of interaction for [Bmim][BF₄] on modified silica surface.

group of the analytes. Therefore, it can effectively shield the residual silanols and improve the peak shapes, as well as decrease the retention time of the analytes.

Both of chlorogenic acid and caffeic acid are weak acids, so they complete when interacting with the stationary phase. Chlorogenic acid is more effective than caffeic acid. Therefore the retention time of chlorogenic acid is decreased while of caffeic acid increased. Rutin is not acid and contains several hydroxyl groups. The hydrogen bonds of it interact with the IL coated stationary phase and the retention time increases in the presence of IL in the mobile phase.

Effect of [Bmim][BF₄] concentration :

Fig. 5 shows the dependency of retention factors (*k*) along with error bars of chlorogenic acid, caffeic acid and rutin on concentration of [Bmim][BF₄] (0–1.0 mM) in the mobile phase at pH 4. The results show that the retention time of chlorogenic acid (*k*₁) decreases with increasing [Bmim][BF₄] concentration, reaching a minimum at 0.75 mM. On the other hand, the retention times of caffeic acid (*k*₂) and rutin (*k*₃) increase initially with increasing [Bmim][BF₄] concentration and then decrease. Interestingly, they also have a minimum at 0.75 mM

Fig. 3. Chromatogram of (1) chlorogenic acid, (2) caffeic acid and (3) rutin in ACN/water (20/80, v/v) mobile phase.

Fig. 4. Chromatogram of (1) chlorogenic acid, (2) caffeic acid and (3) rutin in ACN/water (20/80, v/v) mobile phase containing 0.5 mM [Bmim][BF₄] as additives.

Fig. 5. The error bar of retention factor (k) for (1) chlorogenic acid, (2) caffeic acid and (3) rutin

Fig. 6. The error bar of resolution (R) between chlorogenic acid and caffeic acid.

Fig. 7. The error bar of resolution (R) between caffeic acid and rutin.

[Bmim][BF₄] and a maximum at 0.25 mM [Bmim][BF₄] concentration. As mentioned above, there is competition between chlorogenic acid and caffeic acid, and the retention mechanism of rutin is different from a weak acid. The addition of an ionic liquid causes competition between imidazolium cations and the polar group of analytes for silanol groups on the alkylsilica surface, which results in a significant decrease in the retention of the analytes. When the concentration of the IL is fixed, the imidazolium cations will take the primary factor in the competition with the polar group of analytes, which results in an increase in the retention.

Fig. 6 shows the resolution of chlorogenic acid and caffeic acid, and Fig. 7 shows the resolution of caffeic acid and rutin. Both resolutions have a maximum at 0.50 mM [Bmim][BF₄]. It shows that 0.50 mM [Bmim][BF₄] is the optimal concentration for separation.

Conclusions :

The separation of three components (chlorogenic acid, caffeic acid and rutin) in *Herba Artemisiae Scopariae* was carried out using [Bmim][BF₄] as an additive in the mobile phase, ACN/water (20/80, v/v). The results showed that [Bmim][BF₄] is quite effective in retaining the three components on C₁₈ column 0.50 mM of [Bmim][BF₄] being the optimal concentration for separation. The mechanism of retention in the column was examined. Chlorogenic acid and caffeic acid are weak acids, and there is competition between them for the IL and stationary phase. On the other hand, rutin has several hydroxyl groups which can interact with the IL via H-bond. These results confirmed that the application of [Bmim][BF₄] to HPLC is a simple and effective way of separating compounds in *Herba Artemisiae Scopariae*. The study on the application of ionic liquids to separate other compounds in plants is in progress.

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